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BPP-257

Microirrigation system for horticultural crops for arid and semi-arid niches

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Very large hectare of land of Western Rajasthan has poor agriculture specifically under rabi and summer season with limited water availability. In this era of globalization, advanced technology is penetrating at ground level but very limited and only to those who has sufficient water resources. Remaining majority of farmers, wish to introduce water efficient drip irrigation but they only know traditional way of farming where returns from drip system are not quite worthy for traditional crops like Bajra, Mustard, Wheat, *etc.* Drip irrigation holds considerable importance in sustaining the survival and rhizosphere enrichment strategy under adverse vagaries of nature in arid and semi-arid water scarce niche. Semi-arid and arid has its own richness in Ker, Sangari (khejri), Kumat, kankeda (*Momordica dioca*), Ber, *etc.* these are premium crops of market with good post-harvest life. These traditional crops can be popularized and can be supported for better survival and production through use of micro irrigation system. Sustaining horticulture with a hope of strengthening economic livelihood is a key determinant to support the farmers of arid and semi-arid regions. The adoption of suitable micro-irrigation system along with holding of water in reservoirs or suitable catchment methods will be a future support system in transforming the lives of rural inhabitants by switching over to horticultural crops over traditional ones.

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Nanoparticles in horticultural crops

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Nanotechnology is manipulating matter at scales measurable in nanometre (1-100 nm) at least in one dimension. At nanoscale, the face area of the patches is veritably large relative to their small size, which can make them veritably reactive. Due to this, the abecedarian parcels of the matter at nano-scale may differ from that of corresponding bulk material. Size of the nanoparticle (NPs) must be considered as a significant parameter to study the uptake in plants as various barriers confined within the plants are in the range of micrometre (mm) to nanometre (nm). NPs follow the apoplast and the symplast pathways. The symplastic pathway allows movement through the cytoplasm of conterminous cells, whereas the apoplastic pathway allows inflow through the extracellular spaces involving cell walls of bordering cells and xylem vessels. The cell-to-cell movement takes place through the passage plasmodesmata, serving as a cytoplasmic ground to grease flyspeck movement between neighbouring

cells. Nanomaterials (NM) can be effectively used in germination and growth. The carbon nanotubes can be used as controllers of seed germination and factory growth. The capability of NMs to access the hard coating of seeds and allow water importation is the deciding factor for increased growth and vigour. NPs made of mesoporous silica (MSNs) can ameliorate photosynthesis by interacting with chloroplasts, performing in enhanced seed germination, increased total protein, and chlorophyll content. NPs can mimic the exertion of antioxidant enzymes in the form of nano-enzymes that can scavenge from oxidative stress. Water filtration may be bettered with the use of Nanofiber membranes and the use of nano biocides, which appear promising effective. Pervious concave silica NPs (PHSNs) with validamycin (fungicide) acts as an effective transport structure of water - answerable fungicide to control numerous conditions. Nano-mixes were precious to constructions of fungicides also it might be active in contradiction of the multitudinous pests in crop. Likewise, canvas- loaded NPs were more salutary on behalf of medications of nano- fungicides. Nano silica can be effectively used as a nano fungicide. ZnONPs and MgO NPs show antifungal exertion against *Alternaria alternate*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Mucor plumbeus*. ZnO and MgO NPs are active antibacterial agents. In post-harvest technology of fruits and vegetables, the nanotechnology approach is helpful for controlling post-harvest conditions; introducing a new invention for packaging flicks; precluding impact of feasts and unsafe shafts; perfecting packaging appearance; and helping for labelling fresh products using the multiple chips (nano biosensors). Therefore, it's prognosticated that nanotechnology will come one of the most important forces for invention in the food packaging assiduity.

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Elasticity in tuber crops to drought

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Potatoes and cassava are two of the world's most significant food crops, ranking in the top six. They produce more water than cereals and are regarded as one of the most energy-efficient crops. When drought happened during the tuberization period, yields were lower than when drought struck during the vegetative phase. Drought sensitivity is high in both cassava and sweet potato during storage root initiation. Tuber malformation in potatoes is caused by water stress during tuber bulking. Yam is perhaps the only root/tuber species that has been documented to have high drought resistance soon after planting. Despite their scant fine root structure, cassava develops thinner and deeper roots, allowing them to access subsoil water. During drought, water-stressed cassava plants reduce carbon cost by ceasing osmolytes production. Droughts during tuber commencement and tuber bulking significantly affect sweet potato production. At a significantly lower water potential (-1.3 MPa) than potato leaves, leaves wilt permanently. Irrigation at a moisture depletion level of 60% could boost root yield by 24% when compared to non-irrigated sweet potatoes. Yams may thrive in areas where annual rainfall is as low as 500 mm, however production potential is limited. New yam plants sprout with significant vine length expansion after surviving a dry period (sometimes exceeding two meters). Potassium